

Ecofriendly energetic oxidizer-hydrazinium nitroformate (HNF) and propellants based on HNF[†]

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Limited research work carried out at HEMRL has made it possible to obtain high purity hydrazinium nitroformate (HNF) by adopting an innovative synthesis approach of usage of specific surface active agent and following the methods reported in literature. The morphological characteristics of HNF were modified by sulfo-succinate class of surfactant and crystals akin to processing in propellant binder matrix were obtained. HNF was fully characterized by applying instrumental techniques including UV/FTIR/¹H NMR/SEM. A defect-free castable CMDB formulation was made, as a combined effect of purity and morphology of HNF as well as making use of physicochemical characteristics of double base matrix in place of commonly used polybutadiene binders. The formulation studied is capable of producing I_{sp} of 270 s (theoretical) with higher burning rates than current systems. Thermal studies carried out by applying DSC, revealed interaction between two-stage decomposition products of HNF and single-stage decomposition species of double base matrix. This may be attributed to the involvement of exothermic surface/near surface decomposition of HNF at temperatures lower than that of double base matrix. HNF intermixed with high energy materials having high decomposition temperature (thermally stable explosives) like cyclotetramethylenetetranitramine (HMX), hexanitrohexaazaisowurtzitane (HNIW), triaminotrinitrobenzene (TATB) and tetranitrodibenzotetraazapentalene (TACOT) did not influence their decomposition behavior. Both HNF and thermally stable energetic explosives decomposed independently.

Modern ammonium perchlorate (AP) and cyclotrimethylenetrinitramine (RDX) / cyclotetramethylenetetranitramine (HMX) based composite and composite modified double base (CMDB) propellants are beset with the problem of pollution producing combustion products and low burning rates respectively¹. New directions in propellant research are aimed at realizing dual objective of ecofriendly combustion products and higher energy coupled with superior burning rates. Ammonium dinitramide (ADN) and hydrazinium nitroformate (HNF) have emerged as new candidate oxidizers in the last decade for next generation propellants. These oxidizers offer superior heat of formation (ΔH_f) than AP and much higher oxygen balance than RDX/HMX (Table 1). Moreover, they undergo highly exothermic combustion reactions near the surface, resulting in efficient heat feedback to deflagrating surface leading to high burning rates^{2,3}.

HNF has advantage over ADN in terms of higher melting point and higher decomposition temperature, which are relevant from application point of view. Moreover, HNF is non-hygroscopic, while ADN is highly susceptible to moisture, resulting in problems of obtaining defect-free propellants. Kinetic parameters determined by monitoring gas evolution suggest that low temperature decomposition of HNF is a first order reaction and it can be stored for several years

Table 1. Potential oxidizers/HEMs*

Oxidizer	Formula	ΔH_f kJ mol ⁻¹	Oxygen balance (%)	Density (g/cm ³)	Melting point/ Decomp. temp. (°C)
AP	NH ₄ ClO ₄	-298	34	1.9	452 (d)
ADN		-151	26	1.8	92.5
HNF		-71	13	1.9	115
RDX		63	-22	1.8	204
HMX		76	-22	1.9	280
HNIW		454	-11	2.1	195

*Ref. 3.

without deterioration. However, major concern is its high friction sensitivity (BAM ft : 12-16 N). Phlegmatization of HNF by special gels is being attempted to reduce its sensitivity⁴.

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

The preparation methods of HNF have bearing on its stability and sensitivity. Sequence, rate of addition and proportions of reactants as well as their purity are some of the important parameters, which control the purity and stability of HNF. Recrystallization process (cooling/evaporation/solvent-nonsolvent treatment) decides the size and length/diameter (L/D) ratio of crystals of HNF, which in turn influences the processing of the propellant formulations. Sonocrystallization is reported to make a remarkable improvement in morphology of HNF by influencing nucleation behavior and process of crystal growth as well as breaking the crystals⁴.

In addition to the problems associated with purity and crystal structure, utilization of HNF in practical formulations suffers from the drawback of its incompatibility with workhorse binder hydroxy terminated polybutadiene (HTPB), due to transfer of hydrogen from HNF to nitrogen (in NCO group) of isocyanates (toluene/hexamethylene diisocyanate) used as curatives for HTPB. It is also reported that C=C present in HTPB backbone gets oxidized by HNF leading to deterioration of mechanical properties of binder. Various approaches have been attempted to overcome these problems including programming the reactions between isocyanates and binder by adjusting their ratios. Recently, researchers have claimed a castable HTPB based propellant containing 80% HNF of different crystal sizes and recommended Desmodur-VL as curative. The mechanical properties of the propellant (Young's modulus 7.9–8.4 MPa and maximum stress 0.7–0.8 MPa) are comparable to conventional composite propellant. The composition could be stored without showing degradation effects for one year⁵. However, details of propellant composition (stabilizer/antioxidant) and process parameters have not been disclosed.

The emergence of new energetic binders, in addition to powerful explosive, has opened new vistas of research in the area of advanced solid propellants. Major advantages of energetic polymers are that they allow partitioning of energy due to the presence of exothermally decomposing substituents (N₃)/oxygen-rich groups (ONO₂) and their moderate requirement of oxygen because of relatively lower C/H content. Owing to peculiar structural features and physicochemical characteristics, new oxidizer and polymeric binders complement each other resulting in the possibilities of engineering solid propellants approaching Isp levels of 300 s. Glycidylazide polymer (GAP) and poly-3-nitromethoxy-3-methyloxetane (PNMMO) are fast emerging as binder suitable for HNF propellants. However, processing, compatibility and sensitivity characteristics of these systems need more attention^{3,5,6}.

The properties of HNF reported in open literature are at variance because of the different methodologies followed by various labs/plants and contamination of the product with different impurities as well as dissimilar crystal characteristics. Therefore, major challenge faced by propellant chemist is to obtain HNF and binder slurry akin to casting and realizing desired structural integrity of the monolithic propellant.

In view of these problems, R&D work is on all over the globe to develop modified synthetic route/surface treatment and optimization of propellant formulations. It is expected that systematic analysis of the new data and overlapping results generated in various laboratories can provide a direction for the future course of action for making HNF based propellants a practical reality. This paper discusses the approach for synthesis of high purity HNF adopted in our laboratory. The details regarding its characterization are also included. Double base matrix, better understood than new energetic polymers, was selected as binder in an attempt to obtain a castable HNF based propellant. Strand burning rates of the propellant were determined at different pressures. An attempt has been also made to understand the decomposition/combustion process by applying DSC. In an attempt to enhance the thermal decomposition temperature of HNF, it was mixed with energetic compounds decomposing at temperature >200° in 1:1 proportion. Cyclotetramethylenetetranitramine (HMX), hexanitrohexaaisowurtzitan (HNIW) and thermally stable explosives, namely, triaminotrinitrobenzene (TATB)/tetranitrodibenzotetraazapentalene (TACOT) were evaluated. DSC was used to study thermal decomposition pattern of the mix.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of HNF :

HNF, a salt of weak base (hydrazine) and weak acid (nitroform-NF), was synthesized in two steps, namely, preparation of NF, followed by its neutralization with hydrazine. Initial reported methods of preparation of NF, involving nitration of acetylene/acetone are associated with hazards due to high exothermicity of the reaction in conjunction with volatility/flammability of starting materials. Another hazardous step involved in HNF synthesis was separation of NF from the reaction mixture by vacuum distillation requiring high temperatures. Yet another problem faced was the formation of azeotropic mixture of NF with HNO₃. We have established a relatively safe synthesis and separation method for NF and HNF recrystallization process on the lines of the methods reported by Frankel *et al.*^{7,8} and Meulenbrugge⁹. The method adopted at HEMRL is essentially similar to

that reported by Schyoe *et al.*⁴. However, surface treatment of the recrystallized HNF is a totally a new approach of our methodology^{10,11}. HNF has been produced in a reactor operating at 200 g/batch scale. The outline of the process adopted is given in Fig. 1. This method gives the yield of 25% and the product has melting point (m.p.) in the range of 120–124° (reported 110–124°).

Fig. 1. Flow chart of HNF production process (HEMRL).

Major outcome of the surface treatment process used in the present study appears to be the drastic change in the

Fig. 2. SEM of (a) untreated and (b) treated HNF.

surface structure of HNF crystals as revealed by SEM (Fig. 2). XPS studies conducted suggest high degree of hydrogen bonding¹², which may influence the viscosity/ consistency of the HNF slurry in polymeric binder rendering it non-castable beyond a limit. The surfactant used in the present study may be modifying the surface structure of crystals by masking such active centers.

The purity of HNF was found to be >98% by HPLC. The elemental analysis results (C, 6.66; H, 2.73; N, 38.03%) are in conformity with the theoretical values (C, 6.55; H, 2.75, N, 38.25%). HNF was also characterized by UV, FTIR and ¹H NMR spectra (Fig. 3). UV spectra exhibited absorptions at λ_{max} 210 and 352 nm. It is a combined feature of UV absorption of hydrazine (λ_{max} 210 nm) and NF (λ_{max} 220 and 350 nm). Schoyer *et al.*⁴ suggested that the relative slope of the peak heights of absorptions of HNF at 210 and 350 nm can be used as quality control measure as it can be correlated with the proportions of hydrazine and NF. IR spectra showed NO₂ stretch at 1271 (sym) and 1512 cm⁻¹ (asym) with NO₂ bend at 790 cm⁻¹ as well as NH₃⁺ bend at 1420 and wag at 1180 cm⁻¹. Absorptions at 1100 and 971 cm⁻¹ correspond to N–C–N and N–N. Two sharp signals of relative intensities of 2 : 3 obtained in ¹H NMR at δ 2.01 and 7.7 can be attributed to two different types of hydrogen atoms linked to different nitrogen atoms^{3,4,10–12}.

HNF propellants :

We have adopted a new approach to formulate high performance HNF based CMDB propellants. NC/NG combination (double base binder matrix) was used in place of incompatible HTPB and phthalates, commonly used plasticizers for DB and CMDB systems were replaced by energetic low molecular weight GAP.

Control composition (GAP plasticized DB matrix) exhibited burning rates of the order of 9.7–18 mm/s in the pressure range of 3–9 MPa. Inclusion of 30–40% HNF in DB matrix led to an increase in burning rates of more than 40–95% (Table 2).

Table 2. Burning rates of HNF based CMDB propellants

Com-position	SNC %	CL %	HNF %	Al %	Burning rates (mm/s) at MPa				Burning rate index (3-9 MPa)
					3	5	7	9	
1	60	40	–	–	9.7	12.4	17.5	18.1	0.61
2	30	40	30	–	15.4	18.4	20.8	29.7	0.70
3	25	35	40	–	16.0	22.0	29.5	35.8	0.74
4	20	40	23	17	13.8	20.9	26.5	30.4	0.73

Fig. 3. Characterization of HNF.

In order to realize superior performance level, 17% Al was added at the cost of HNF. These formulations offered burning rates of the order of 14–36 mm/s in the pressure region studied with pressure exponent of 0.7–0.74 and aluminized composition has theoretical I_{sp} of 270 s. Complete characterization of the composition is in progress and attempts are being made to replace NG by other energetic nitroplas-

ticizers to achieve improvements in sensitivity characteristics of the formulation as friction sensitivity was high (2 kg in Julius Peters test).

Thermal decomposition/combustion :

DSC revealed two-stage decomposition of HNF with maxima at 132 and 139° (Fig. 4). These results are in line

Fig. 4. DSC of HNF, DB matrix and CMDB propellants.

with those reported by other researchers¹⁰. Williams and Brill¹³ proposed the following two stages of decomposition of HNF in the temperature range of 123–260° on the basis of the data generated at the heating rate of 600°/s on Pt filament by monitoring the gases evolved during decomposition of HNF using FTIR and FT-Raman spectroscopy :

Koroban *et al.*¹⁴ suggested that other reactions occur simultaneously and major reaction is decomposition of ammonium nitroformate (ANF) :

Thus, the overall exothermicity corresponds to 300 kJ mol⁻¹ and explains the self-sustained combustion of HNF. The activation energy (E_a) of the decomposition of HNF obtained for the product synthesized by the method described in the present study¹² was ~150 kJ mol⁻¹ which is close to that obtained by Schoyer *et al.*⁴ for the HNF obtained in TNO, The Netherlands plant, by monitoring rate of gas evolution (147–157 kJ mol⁻¹). The total heat output of HNF decomposition obtained in this investigation was ~2100 J g⁻¹ (Fig. 4).

Double-base propellant (control propellant) underwent single-stage decomposition with maxima at 201° and heat evolution was of the order of 2114 J g⁻¹. It is a well known fact that NC and NG undergo thermal decomposition as homogenous mix in the temperature range 170–200°. GAP is

also reported to decompose in more or less similar temperature region. Basic decomposition process of double-base matrix involves cleavage of O-NO₂ bond followed by interaction of oxides with hydrocarbons/aldehydes. The sequential interactions between these moieties manifest in unidirectional flame comprising fizz, dark and luminous zones¹. GAP decomposes with exothermic cleavage of azide structure with major energy release in sub-surface region¹⁵.

DSC of 30% HNF-CMDB propellant exhibited basic features of decomposition of HNF and DB matrix. However, an additional peak was observed as shoulder to HNF exotherm with T_m of 154°, suggesting an interaction between decomposition products of HNF and DB matrix. DSC output of 40% HNF-CMDB propellant also showed similar features. As HNF undergoes exothermic decomposition in condensed phase as interpreted by the absence of HNF aerosol during fast thermal decomposition studies carried out by Williams and Brill¹³, it may be facilitating the decomposition of DB matrix by providing oxides of nitrogen, the major oxidizing species of these systems, at faster pace than in case of double-base matrix alone. Trends obtained for heat evolution in case of HNF-based propellants further confirm occurrence of such exothermic interactions, as 30–40% HNF-CMDB propellant evolved 731–1183 J g⁻¹ heat in the temperature region of 122–167°, which is higher than that predicted for 30–40% fraction of HNF. The decrease in heat evolution on incorporation of Al may be attributed to its heat sink effect as well as formation of agglomerates and non-participation of Al in condensed phase reactions.

Energetic nitramines - HNIW and HMX decomposing in the temperature range of 250–280° did not influence the

Fig. 5. DSC of HNF with nitramines and thermally stable explosives (1 : 1).

decomposition of HNF and vice versa as revealed by DSC pattern of their 1 : 1 weight mix (Fig. 5). This means that both nitramines studied and HNF decompose independently without any interaction among their decomposition products. Thermally stable compounds TATB and TACOT decomposing at 360–410° were also not affected with the decomposition species.

The limited research work carried out in the present study has provided a base for R&D work of HNF and HNF based propellants of futuristic value.

Experimental

HNF synthesis was carried out using fuming nitric acid (conc. >95%), iso-propanol (IPA), ethylene dichloride (EDC) and hydrazine hydrate of A.R. grade. HPLC was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer instrument having micro C18 column with UV-detector operating at 210 nm. A CE EA-1110 instrument was used for elemental analysis. Electronic spectra (aqueous medium) were recorded on a Hitachi 340-C spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 1605 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃/DMSO-*d*₆) on a Bruker spectrometer (300 MHz) with TMS as standard. SEM were recorded on a Phillips instrument.

Control formulation studied during this work comprised of spherical NC (SNC) [NC : 90%, NG : 7%, sym-diethyl area : 3%] : 60% and desensitized NG [NG : 80%, GAP (Mn : 500) : 18%, 2-nitrodiphenylamine : 2%] : 40%. In HNF based propellant formulation, 30–40% HNF was added at the cost of NC/NG matrix. In metallized HNF formulation, 17% Al (15 ± 2μ) was added at the cost of HNF. The propellant compositions were prepared by adopting slurry – cast technique¹⁶. The SNC was mixed with desensitized NG in a planetary mixer and HNF/Al were incorporated step by step in separate instalments. Mixing was continued for 15 min without vacuum and 45 min under vacuum (10 torr) at 25 ± 5°. The slurry obtained was cast under vacuum (2–5 torr) and curing was carried out at 40 ± 2° for 5 days. The purity of all ingredients/explosives used was checked before incorporation.

Burning rates were determined in the pressure range of 3–9 MPa by acoustic emission technique¹⁷. The methodology involved combustion of strands (6 × 6 × 100 mm) in the nitrogen pressurized steel bomb. Acoustic signals generated by the deflagrating sample were sensed by the piezoelectric transducer of resonance frequency of 200 kHz. DSC pattern of propellant samples with respect to HNF and

double base matrix was obtained on a Perkin-Elmer DSC-7 instrument at 10°/min heating rate in N₂ atmosphere.

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